

AnganConnect: A Comprehensive Digital Solution for Housing Societies

Fariha Chowdhury Tabia

Student, Computer Science and Engineering, Lovely Professional University, Punjab, India
farihachowdhury004@gmail.com

Abstract

In today's expeditious modern world with buzzing residential community, keeping things running effectively can be quite a challenging. The AanganConnect Housing Society Management is developed as a global web development application using Node JS, EJS and MongoDB, System is used to address this issue. This study examines the creation of a Society Management System, a comprehensive online platform that is a digital solution intended to simplify a number of facets of communal living. Admins can use such systems to effectively manage their tasks and activities rather than wasting hours going through paperwork or locating residents by hand for crucial updates. The system seeks to improve resident convenience by simplifying and streamlining processes like document uploads, bill payments, and complaint reporting, among others. The project's main goal is to protect resident personal documents and information from misuse and preventing them from being prone to unauthorized access by guaranteeing the highest level of security. Additionally, admin can provide transparency by enabling user to track how their information and data are being used and to enable them to update their profile information anytime. Our goal in conducting this research is to address the

changing demands of contemporary living spaces and offer a scalable solution that meets the demands of the current generation. By automating repetitive tasks, centralizing information and communication, and improving security measures, the project's overall goal is to lessen the administrative load on building secretaries and help users to have an accessibility of an effective and smooth management portal.

Keywords

Society Management, API, Web Portal, Web Development, Database, Residents, Housing Society, Transparency, Admin.

1. Introduction

The demand for online web based management systems and online portals has increased significantly in last few years as it's very hard to maintain the data manually and store it. Since web services have become more and more strong, reliable and distributive, web based computing has tremendously changed our life. As internet has become as one of the easiest available and accessible commodity web-based computing provides an effective platform for communication via a web based management systems.

The web-based society management system primarily features an effective solution for the day-to-day needs of both residents and admins of the society. It keeps all of the information about the housing system in one location for easy access by all members of the community, as it is currently very difficult to maintain and store the data manually. Moreover, it provides security for society members, the Web Based Management System for Housing Society allows us to keep track of visitors, societies, cities and everyone else by storing the data in a database (MongoDB). We can easily lower the fraud rate in this way. The primary goal of this project is to create a housing society management system that is easy to use and effective for both individual and commercial use. Node.js and EJS are used in the implementation of this application.

By leveraging automation, digitalization, and AI-driven interactions, AnganConnect Society Management System revolutionizes housing society management, fostering better communication, improving administrative efficiency, and ensuring a seamless living experience for residents. This paper explores the development, implementation, and impact of E-Society in modernizing community management [2] [3] [4].

2. Literature Review:

Society management systems have greatly advanced due to advancements in digital technologies, allowing housing societies to function more efficiently and smoothly. Numerous research and current solutions

emphasize the difficulties and advantages of digital transformation in managing residential communities. This section examines pertinent literature concerning housing society management systems, API-based architectures, shared occupancy, multi-tenant frameworks, and the impact of AI on improving user experience [2] [3].

I. Housing Society Management System:

The Housing Society Management System was developed to oversee the day-to-day activities of a cooperative society and enhance the current state of society. The proposed study's objective was to create online resources for handling grievances in gated and guarded communities. This system was created to take into account the difficulties in overseeing day-to-day operations and resolving grievances in gated communities. All the necessary security measures are in place in these communities to guarantee the residents' safety and security. However, the management has found that the current messaging-based complaint raising process is inefficient and time-consuming. We advise creating web-based applications to increase the efficiency of this procedure. These applications offer a more effective and convenient way to handle complaints. Real complaints are handled by the application's effectiveness, and the status of these complaints is tracked. The goal of this system is to improve communication and optimize the processes [3].

II. Society management application on

android: The Society Management System was created to manage the daily

operations of a cooperative society and improve the existing condition of the society. The aim of the proposed study was to develop online tools for addressing complaints in gated and guarded communities. This system was developed to address the challenges of managing daily operations and handling complaints in gated communities. All essential security protocols are established in these communities to ensure the safety and protection of the residents. Nonetheless, the management has discovered that the existing process for raising complaints via messaging is ineffective and requires too much time. We recommend developing online applications to enhance the effectiveness of this process. These applications provide a more efficient and convenient method for managing complaints. Genuine complaints are addressed by the application's efficiency, and the progress of these complaints is monitored. The objective of this system is to enhance communication and streamline processes [4].

III. Introduction to AI Chatbots: The impact of the current technological period on civilization is enormous. Since the development of the best virtual assistants, chatbots have gained a significant popularity in the conversational services industry. Chatbots are computer programs that comprehend and process natural language. In addition to helping users with chores like finding the closest restaurant or purchasing a movie ticket, chatbots can also be a source of amusement, contribute significantly to home automation projects, offer advice on

company strategy, and assist in other ways. We shall explain the definition of a chatbot and its various varieties in this paper. Additionally, we suggest a classification based on requirements, usefulness, and current market trends [15].

IV. Cloud based Housing Society Management System:

To improve the current condition of society to be more straightforward Direct and impactful, this article highlights a structure that enables users to manage housing societies through a web-based, cloud-supported system. At present, each city hosts numerous communities. Asset Monitoring, internet upkeep fees, alert systems, expenses Monitoring and the generation of annual reports are simply some of the benefits provided by societal management systems. Individuals within this system are able to engage with each other based on their common interests. Cloud-based applications allow for easy adjustments to cater to societal demands. This system can accommodate numerous users without the need for the developer's participation. The key attribute of this system is that it is easy to use and completely automated. It's additionally based in the cloud. Within the system, there exist multiple features accessible. For instance, there exists a digital voting system for different positions in society, including secretary, chairperson, and treasurer. The system provides a comprehensive database of each societal member, enabling users to swiftly locate contact details for anyone they decide to communicate with. The

system intends to simplify communication [6].

V. Effectiveness of Payment Gateway in

E- Commerce: This study's goal is to determine the advantages of using gateway payments for utility bill Payments transactions for both buyers and sellers. The authors of this discussion explained the payment gateway's operation using pictures and the journal's study methodology. According to the study's findings, customers may experience the convenience and security of transactions through payment gateways, while sellers can complete large transactions swiftly and securely. This is a result of simultaneous Payment Gateway queries. Finding out the advantages and operational technique of payment for both customers and sellers is the study's conclusion [7].

3. Existing System

In the present situations, housing society management authorities use an outdated and less secure method for user authentication and storing personal data. Many of societies also have started using automated chat systems which are restricted to answering general queries rather than society related ones. The complaint-raising system doesn't provide varieties and subsections for complaints. Here some. The payments are always prone to cyber frauds and transactions are less secure[2] [3] [4].

I. User data and authentication

In most of current managements systems user's data and information are always at

risk of being exposed to any random person on the server and user's authentication is also often compromised.

Many times it happens that user's passwords are not encrypted properly which always leaves a risk of them being compromised. Often, user authentication methods rely on simple password-based systems, which are always vulnerable and prone to common cyber-attacks like brute force or phishing. Moreover, the lack of multi-factor authentication further accelerates the risk, as a single compromised password can grant attackers full access to user accounts and other personal information.

The inability to upgrade and patch security flaws in the system is another serious problem. The use of antiquated software by many management platforms makes them more vulnerable to attackers. Many times, when data is carried across a network without encryption, private information is left vulnerable, which makes it simpler for hackers to intercept and abuse the data.

II. Automated Chat Bots

These systems work well as a general chat window, but they don't offer a dedicated setting for certain purposes, which leads to pointless information sharing taking precedence over the core topic.

These chat bots are not very well trained for specific management systems and don't have the capability to provide specific management system related answer They usually end up giving same responses to all the queries, which is not

required and does not help the user in addressing their doubts[2] [5].

III. Complaints Registration

Usually these society management systems have one common complaint registration section where residents or users can raise their complaints that lacks in analyzing the seriousness of the complaints and prioritizing any specific type of complaint.

It's a common fact that not all complaints when registered requires an urgent and immediate actions However, there are many that do, and failing to prioritize these can lead to delays and dissatisfaction among residents.

Proper communication between the one who registered the complaint and admin should be maintained but in usual cases it's not there and which creates hindrances in providing the status the complaint registered. [2][10].

IV. Payment Gateways

Bill and rent payments in the society managements system is one of the most difficult task as it requires high level of security and authenticity. Many society management systems don't have the bill and rents payment facility and who have and those who have their payments systems are always prone to cyber-attacks and frauds.

The majority of these society managements systems doesn't provides the facilities of download bills to its users or residents. Furthermore these society management systems don't issue any

receipts after completion of the payments and because of that users are left without any convenient access to previous transactions details or any kind of proof of their payments and transactions which makes future reference or dispute resolution more difficult.

Existing society management systems doesn't provide admin the feature to keep a track of all the payments being done and which residents are yet required to make the payments and who has already make the payments which makes it very difficult of the admins to maintain payment history as they have to manually check everyone's payment.

4. Proposed Idea

To find solutions of the problems there in other society management system and to overcome the drawbacks this paper intends to provide a Secure and Smart Housing Society Management System that improves security, efficiency, and user convenience in response to the difficulties faced by current housing society management systems. Improving user authentication, incorporating a trained chatbot for society related specific queries, upgrading the complaint registration process and ensuring safe online payments are the main objectives of the suggested solution[4] [5] [8].

5. Methodology

1. These are the distinct features from existing society managements systems
2. Enhanced Data Security and User Authentication.

3. Trained Chatbot for Society-Specific Queries

4. Smart Complaint Management System distinct

5. Transparent and Secure Payments distinct

I. Enhanced Data Security and User Authentication:

The user's password is properly encrypted and even the system administrator cannot view the password of any resident from the database of any resident and to achieve this hashed and salted passwords have been used to prevent unauthorized access [1] [9][10].

Figure-1 Encrypted Data

OTP verification is made necessary and it is done before registering any resident to check the authenticity of the submitted data and prevent any fake accounts with fake details being registered.

To address vulnerabilities and defend against major online threats, system's database is monitored frequently, security patches and updates are done on a regular basis [1].

II. Trained Chatbot for Society-Specific Queries:

ChatBot are required to provide context based answers in order to address the queries of the user and when the answers are not context based and are not specific according to what is being asked, the user don't have a good experience with the chatbot and usually his queries remains unaddressed.

To guarantee meaningful, context-based responses, the chatbot uses the Gemini model. The model will be able to understand the specific information and changes about each society as it is trained with data relating to that society. This will allow it to respond to specific questions about visitors, admins, society notices, society services and other topics.

Based on the resident's profile and previous interactions, the chatbot will provide customized responses. The bot will provide tailored responses to residents' inquiries regarding society and its other features. For day-to-day operations like filing complaints or verifying payment information, checking status of the complaints registered, the chatbot will offer prompt assistance. If the problems are complicated and required some seriousness, the chatbot will forward the matter to an administrator for prompt resolution [5] [9].

Figure-2 AI automated Chabot [5]

III. Smart Complaint Management System

The Complaint section improves and streamlines complaint handling by categorizing issues into high-priority and low-priority and also provides the status of the complaints so that the user can track the status of the regisitered issue. This ensures that urgent matters are addressed first and provided updated status, improving response times and residents satisfaction.

The system will include specific subsections like maintenance, billing, and lost and found to allow for more accurate complaint reporting. This helps in identifying the nature of the issue and prioritizing it accordingly. Subsection like “Lost and Found” helps in providing specific category to the complaints which will help in addressing the issues more effectively and efficiently[10].

Figure-3 Complaint Registration [2] [3]

Figure-3.1 Lost and Found [4]

IV. Transparent and Secure Payments

Transparent and Secure Payment System ensures that all bills and rents related payments are well within the housing society and they are secured, traceable, and easy to manage. This system will integrate several advanced features to protect residents and provide a seamless payment experience.

Figure-4 Bill Generation

Stripe payment gateway integration helps in securing the transactions as they are widely trusted and one of the most secure platform. It also offers fraud detection measures like advanced machine learning algorithms to spot suspicious activities and prevent unauthorized transactions

Figure 4.2- Stripe Payment Gateway [7]

The admins always have the accessibility of all the payments being done. Admins can check paid and unpaid residents in the Accounting section and request them or provide them a reminder for completion of the bill and rent payments [7].

Figure 4.1- Payment Receipt

Before initialising the payments the residents can download the bill for their references. After successful payments it's very important to have receipt of the transactions, and this payment system provides the receipt of all the transactions which helps in tracking all the precious transactions being done.

Resident	Flat	Status	Due
Gaurav Singh	8	UNPAID	2171
Shrey Kumar	06	PAID	0
Rishabh Singh	13	PAID	0

Figure 4.3- Payment Receipt

6. CHALLENGES

A number of issues need to be resolved throughout the creation and deployment of the suggested system, despite the fact that it promises notable enhancements in security, user experience, and operational efficiency. Among these difficulties are:

I. Data Privacy and Security Concerns:

One of the biggest challenges is making sure that private resident data, such as financial and personal information, is protected from any sort of cyber attacks. Even with hashed passwords and end-to-end encryption, the system needs to always keep ahead of new threats and weaknesses. Frequent security patches and upgrades are essential but at the same time it can be difficult to manage them across platforms without compromising data integrity or user access [8] [10].

II. Integrating Multiple Systems: The Stripe payment gateway, AI Chabot, and other systems must all smoothly and seamlessly integrate with the Society Management System. These integrations frequently call for detailed process, data format, and system integration. It is a technical problem to provide seamless data interchange and functionality across many platforms. Transitioning from an outdated system to a more secure and efficient system can be challenging, and always requiring appropriate data migration techniques and making sure there is little hindrances and problem in achieving that [6].

III. Training Chabot

The AI chatbot must be trained using specific and precise data. This means we are required to collect lot of information from each society and keep it updated regularly as protocols, notices, and events change. To guarantee that it provides accurate, meaningful, and context-based responses, the Gemini model needs to be continuously improved. Irrelevant

responses or wrong interpretation and repetitive responses for every queries raised by users might annoy the users and result in low system adoption. If the system is not built with an intelligent escalation mechanism, it may also be difficult to handle complex questions and escalation to human administrators without overtaxing the administrative team.

IV. Categorizing Complaints:

It might be tedious task to create a complaint section which is both effective and user-friendly while accurately categorizing and prioritizing issues. A clever decision-making algorithm and efficient monitoring are necessary to guarantee that complaints are forwarded to the appropriate department (such as maintenance or lost and found) and swiftly addressed. To ensure that critical issues are handled first without ignoring other significant instances, the "Lost and Found" system must be accurate in differentiating between legitimate and fraudulent complaints and the queries related to it should be given the top level of priority and importance.

7. Conclusion

The AanganConnect Housing Society System tackles many major issues by improving authenticity, security, efficiency, and user experience which lacks in many existing society managements systems. The proposed system guarantees data privacy and safety by putting robust authentication methods in place, such as OTP verification and encrypted passwords. The AI-powered Chabot enhances

communication by giving precise, context-based responses after being trained with society specific data and information. The complaints are categorized, urgent concerns are given priority, and real-time tracking is made possible with the help of organized complaint management system. The Stripe-integrated secure payment system ensures safe and secure transactions, offers payments receipts allowing the residents to track their previous payments, and lets users download previous invoices.

With perpetual updations, security enhancements, and user-friendly features, this system offers a more reliable and efficient solution for modern housing societies, improving overall management and resident satisfaction.

8. References

- [1]. Muhammad Barbar, Fazlullah Khan, Waseem Iqbal, Abid Yahy “A Secured Data Management Scheme for Smart Societies in Industrial Internet of Things Environment” (2016)
- [2]. Shivganga Vishal Gavhane, Rutuja Vatharkar, Swati Sonar, Pratiksha Patil, “Study of Implementation of Society Management System” (Dec 2015)
- [3]. Likhitha Reddy Eddala, “Web Based Management System for Housing Society” (Aug 2023)
- [4]. Omkar Singh, Aditee Lakhan, Jyoti Gupta, “Implementation of an Android Application for Management of Housing Society” (2015)
- [5]. Aishwarya Gupta, “Introduction to AI Chatbots” (July 2020)
- [6]. Saurabh Malgaonkar, Vivek Maurya, Mukul Kulkarni, Gurtej Singh Majithia, “Multipurpose Android Based Mobile Notifier” (2014)
- [7]. Momin Mukherjee, Sahadev Roy “E-Commerce and Online Payment in the Modern Era” (May 2015)
- [8] SHAO, Guo-hong, “Application Development Research Based on Android Platform” (2014)
- [9]. Mayank Thacker, Lay Shah , Manan Shah, “Society sync – Digitalize society management systems with artificial intelligence technologies”(Aug 2022)
- [10]. Yavuz Selim Yilmaz, Bahadir Ismail Aydin, Murat Demirbas, “Google Cloud Messaging (GCM): An Evaluation”(2014)